

THE WORLD OF PLANTS IN THE URBAN FLORA OF FERGANA CITY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7188059>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 03rd October 2022

Accepted: 07th October 2022

Online: 12th October 2022

KEY WORDS

biodiversity, ecosystem,
technogenic, urbanization,
alkaloids, glycoside,
antropogenic factor, biomass.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that Fergana Valley has a pleasant nature and a moderate climate the conditions here are rich and diverse examples of plants and animals requires spreading. But it is developing rapidly in the region impact of man-made, social urbanization, demographic processes on the natural environment is showing. There are objective and subjective reasons for this. Fergana the geographical location of the valley is deep and surrounded by high mountains the fact that it is wrapped has a negative effect on the atmospheric air circulation. Valley chemical, automobile industry, oil extraction, furniture industry, cotton in the regions waste is released into the environment by cleaning and other factories. As in other places, the continuous increase in the number of vehicles and the atmosphere is polluted due to gases and chemical compounds coming out of them is

ABSTRACT

This article tries to give a general idea about the unique flora of the Fergana city, their biomass and the impact of anthropogenic factors on them. The peculiarities of plants in Fergana city and their protection are fully explained.

going Also, negative aspects are felt in the state of water and soil.

Today, the biodiversity of flora and fauna is preserved stay, effective use of them are among the current problems.

There are 27,000 rare and endangered species in Uzbekistan existing - improving the protection of biodiversity should be a priority need.

The interesting "positive side" of the global quarantine is not only clear skies and less pollution, but wild animals dominated by humans was to return to cities and other settlements. COVID-19 is ours our presence, actions and inactions have a direct impact on biodiversity showed that he would.

It is known that the Fergana Valley is a rich and diverse world of plants among them are various plants that are an important source of food for bees very common. Succulent plants in all zones, as well as It is a highland where beekeeping is well developed in all vegetation covers and

can be found a lot in mountainous regions. Big in mobile beekeeping Among the important honey plants of the mountainous zone are akkur ai, kavar, Shashir, Chitir, Sassik Kavrak and Shirach are examples. Fergana Valley is rich in various plant species. Covered by natural vegetation deer grass, tograyhon, burchak, lion's tail, mehriqiya, zufo, gulhayri, shashir, afghan shashir, ox tongue, yongyi chqa, kashqarbeda, sebarga, shirach, tashkakra, flax, marmarak, mavrak, lalaqizgaldok, kisrak (perovskaya), aiktovan, andiz, geranium, jambil, hyssop, hemp, lemongrass, etc. grows.

In the famous Shakhimardan mountains of the Fergana valley, Uzbekistan the Republic is included in the "Red Book" and considered unique There are limited number of plants rich in alkaloids and glycosides found in fields. Currently, it is anthropogenic that has a negative effect on them Due to the factors, their natural populations fell into a bad state and recovery the process is slowing down. As a result, their areas are reduced and their reserves are tight is decreasing. With this in mind, they are in scattered formations it is necessary to carry out reclamation works and prevent their disappearance. Cultivation of these plants, taking into account their important medicinal value work should be carried out. In addition to these, in the mountainous areas of the valley, It is useful as arrelkuyruq, dalachoy, bozubang, thousand leaf, immortal grass the areas of plants are also decreasing. Their preservation and protection we need to do.

In the valley, various plants are distributed in the basins of the following rivers:

1429 species in the Isfara river basin, 1463 species in the Khodja-Bakirgan river

basin and 1353 species in Shakhimardonsoi basins.

According to estimates, in the basin of Kyzilungur and Karaungur rivers (Fergana mountain) and in the Oloy valley there are plants around 1400-1500. It is estimated that there are about 500 types of fodder for livestock in the territories of the provinces medicinal, about 400 species, more than 300 species with alkaloids, about 200 species and more than 500 types of honey-succulent and other edible plants spread out.

In the surrounding areas of Shakhimardan and Jordan villages, the unique and rare Adonis chrysocyathus, Hyyal (Physochlaina alaica), Turkestan shotarcha (Fumariola turkestanica), Margarita marmaragi (Salvia margaritae), which are considered rare and included in the "Red Book" of Uzbekistan, and scattered Paulsen's and hairy gorse (Lagochilus paulsenii L. pubescens), Olga's sorbaria (Sorbaria olgae). Central in limited areas in the valley Fergana desert has been preserved, 120,000 hectares of sand dunes, 80,000 hectares of salt marshes and orchards have been preserved in these places. Here and in the Syrdarya oasis, there are a lot of orange groves, pine groves and the groves have been preserved.

On sandy and barren substrates, we can find trees and shrubs such as white and black saxavus, cherkes, kandym, kumuzum, and hare's bone. Like all ecosystems of the valley, the desert ecosystem has been negatively affected by anthropogenic factors. Currently, the environmental problems of Margilan and Fergana are in the first place in terms of their dangerous position.

It is known that human being is a bio-social being, it is necessary to preserve his

social and spiritual essence along with his biological essence.

As we can see, these problems affect the natural, social and spiritual development and lead to the deterioration of human health, morale and faith.

The environment is studied on the scale of the boundaries that have normal ecological parameters for living organisms, that is, the boundaries of the biosphere. This problem would not be included in economic problems if the effects of humans on nature were not so great. That is, nature is different it was understood that he would always provide us with unlimited services. But today's situation proves that nature is unable to cope with the excessive influence of humans, that is, it is unable to restore itself. Therefore, each element of nature has its own "capacity" as it has a "limit".

When anthropogenic influence exceeds this limit, it begins to decay. For example, the once flourishing Tigris and Euphrates valleys have turned into deserts due to soil erosion and salinization due to improperly structured irrigation systems and over-planting of agricultural crops. The Uralsk-Volsk deserts are also the result of improper animal husbandry maybe it was. One of the recent ecological crises is the expansion of deserts around the Aral Sea and the increase of salt content in the soil. As a result, the quality of drinking water is deteriorating and various diseases are increasing. The degree of disturbance of the natural state of the environment depends not only on anthropogenic influence, but also on the reaction and properties of natural elements.

The problem of tropical and subtropical forests is of particular concern to humanity. More than half of the forests that need to be cut on a global scale are

being cut down there every year. 160 million hectares of tropical forests have been destroyed, only 11 million hectares are being restored every year. The decline of flora led to the creation of the Red Book.

10-12% of the more than 4,000 plant species in Uzbekistan require protection (4,148 species). The area of the most valuable mountain forests has been reduced dozens of times. A lot of groves and heather forests have been cut down. The area of natural pastures decreased by 6.5 million.

Protection of nature, including its integral part, the world of plants, has become one of the most important problems of our time. It is our sacred duty to protect the diverse, useful and valuable plants of our republic. We have not only useful animal and plant species growing in the territory of Uzbekistan we must preserve every species and species of living animals and present them to future generations at a better level than the present.

Summary. Plants are the primary source of life on earth. They produce 380 billion tons of organic matter per year, of which 330 billion tons go to sea and ocean plants, 40 billion tons to forests, 8-10 billion tons to forests. tons corresponds to meadows. Plants are the basis of life on earth. Plants absorb carbon dioxide from the air and release oxygen as a result of photosynthesis.

There are more than 2,000 flowering plants in the Fergana Valley, among which medicinal plants occupy a special place. The presence of colorful flora and plant cover requires the growth of medicinal plants rich in species. 276 types of medicinal plants are distributed in the valley regions, they belong to 309 genera and 74 families.

422 types (89%) of medicinal plants of Fergana Valley are used in folk medicine and 54 types (11%) in scientific medicine.

Due to the increase in the scale of anthropogenic impacts on the natural vegetation of the Fergana Valley, the areas

of several medicinal species are shrinking and their reserves are decreasing sharply. Some of them remain in need of protection and culturalization.

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